

Two new subspecies of *Alosterna tabacicolor* (DeGeer, 1775) (Coleoptera, Cerambycidae) from the Far East of Russia

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Abstract. *Alosterna tabacicolor kompantsevi* **ssp. n.** from Kunashir Is. and *A. t. toyohara* **ssp. n.** from South Sakhalin Is. are described. Both subspecies are close to *A. t. erythropus* (Gebler, 1841) and *A. t. tenebris* Danilevsky, 2012 (both from mainland Asia) as well as to *A. t. sachalinensis* Danilevsky, 2012 from northern Sakhalin Is. and to *A. t. hirayamai* Fujita, 2018 from the central of Japanese Honshu Is. The distinguishing characters and color illustrations are proposed.

Introduction

The reason for the present article was the publication by Fujita, Hirayama & Akita (2018: 21, 25, 224, Tab. 67, figs 121: 5-7) of *A. tabacicolor fusca* Matsushita, 1930 as a valid name from Rishiri Island, Hokkaido Is., Kuril Iss (Kunashir Is.) and Honshu Is. (Aomori Prefecture). In fact the name is unavailable, as it was shown by Danilevsky (2011: 315): it was introduced as *Alosterna tabacicolor* var. *fusca* Matsushita, 1930 (Mt. Kurodake, Hokkaido) together with *Alosterna tabacicolor* var. *bivittis*: Matsushita, 1930 (Mt. Kurodake, Hokkaido) - two variations from one locality, so “its author expressly gave it infrasubspecific rank” according to the Article 45.6.4. of ICZN (1999). So, the subspecies distributed from Hokkaido to Kunashir needs a new name, which is proposed bellow.

A. tabacicolor (DeGeer, 1775) is distributed all over the north of Palaearctic Region from Spain to Japan, but its geographical variability is not investigated good enough. Only 8 subspecies are already described: *A. t. tabacicolor* from Europe; rather variable *A. t. erythropus* Gebler, 1841(= *bivittis* Motschulsky, 1860) from

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Siberia with often dark to black elytra; rather variable *A. t. subvittata* Reitter, 1885 (= *caucasica* Plavilstshikov, 1936) from Caucasus with often dark elytra; *A. t. azerbaijanica* Danilevsky, 2014 with black elytra from North-East Azerbaijan; *A. t. tokatensis* Pic, 1901 from Turkey, Tokat; *A. t. tenebris* Danilevsky, 2012 with black elytra from Russian Primorie, Korea and northern China; *A. t. sakhalinensis* Danilevsky, 2012 with dark elytra from northern Sakhalin; *A. t. hirayamai* Fujita, 2018 with dark elytra from central Honshu, Japan.

Acronyms of collections.

MD - collection of M.L. Danilevsky (Moscow, Russia);

ML - collection of M.A. Lazarev (Moscow, Russia).

Results

Alosterna tabacicolor kompantsevi ssp. n.

Figs 1-2

Allosterna tabacicolor bivittis, Plavilstshikov, 1936: 306, part. - Siberia, all of Sakhalin, Japan; Krivolutsкая, 1973: 99, part. - Kunashir, Iturup, Shikotan, Japan (Hokkaido, Honshu, Shikoku, Kyushu).

Alosterna tabacicolor var. *fusca* Matsushita, 1930: 24 - Hokkaido.

Allosterna tabacicolor ab. *bivittis*, Tsherepanov, 1979: 239.

Alosterna tabacicolor, Kusama & Takakuwa, 1984: 201, part. - Japan, Kunashir; Ohbayashi N. 2007: 390.

Alosterna tabacicolor bivittis, Tsherepanov, 1996: 80, part. - Siberia, Far East Russia, Sakhalin, Kunashir, Iturup, Shikotan, Japan (Hokkaido, Honshu).

Alosterna tabacicolor erythropus Danilevsky & Smetana, 2010: 96, part. - Siberia, Far East Russia, Japan; Danilevsky, 2020: 120, part. - Siberia, Far East Russia, Japan.

Alosterna tabacicolor fusca, Fujita, Hirayama & Akita, 2018: 27, 224-225 (unavailable name) - Rishiri Island, Hokkaido, Kuril Islands (Kunashir Island) and Honshu (Aomori Prefecture).

Type locality. Kunashir island, Mendeleevo.

Description. Body and prothorax relatively longer than in specimens from the mainland; elytra usually pale, with bigger and denser punctation; light specimens dominate in all populations, though rare black specimens are also known; the area along elytral suture, elytral

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margins and elytral apices are more or less darkened; 1st antennal joint and legs are pale; body length of available specimens, males: 6,6-7,8 mm, female 7,0 mm; width in males: 1,8-1,9 mm, in female: 2,0 mm; body length of “*A. t. fusca*” (sensu Fujita et al., 2018): 6,7-9,4 mm.

Differential diagnosis. The taxon is close to usually very dark *A. t. hirayamai* Fujita, 2018, but most of known specimens are much lighter, though several dark specimens are also known.

Material. Holotype, male, Russia, Kunashir Is., Mendeleevo, 10.7.1977, A. Kompantsev leg. - MD; 5 paratypes; 3 males, 1 female, Russia, Kunashir Is., Tretyakovo, 17.7.1977, A. Kompantsev leg. - MD; 1 female, Japan, Hokkaido, 5.VII.1931, K. Kobayashi leg. - ML.

Distribution. In Russia the taxon is known from Kunashir Is. only. It is widely distributed in Hokkaido, recorded from Rishiri Is., but also known from Honshu Is. (Aomori Prefecture).

Alosterna tabacicolor toyohara ssp. n.

Figs 3-10

Alosterna tabacicolor bivittis, Plavilstshikov, 1936: 306, part. - Siberia, all of Sakhalin, Japan.

Alosterna tabacicolor ab. *bivittis*, Tsherepanov, 1979: 239.

Alosterna tabacicolor bivittis, Tsherepanov, 1996: 80, part. - Siberia, Far East Russia, Sakhalin, Kunashir, Iturup, Shikotan, Japan (Hokkaido, Honshu).

Alosterna tabacicolor erythropus Danilevsky & Smetana, 2010: 96, part. - Siberia, Far East Russia, Japan; Danilevsky, 2020: 120, part. - Siberia, Far East Russia, Japan.

Type locality. Yuzhno-Sakhalinsk environs, southern Sakhalin.

Description. Body and prothorax relatively longer than in *A. t. hirayamai* Fujita, 2018 from Central Honshu (Japan); elytra usually pale in anterior third (about a half of the type series), with smaller and sparser punctation; only 2 males are light along most of elytral surface (darkened laterally and apically); only 1 male with totally black elytra; 1st antennal joint, legs and abdominal apex are always pale; body length in males: 5.7-8.0 mm, width: 1,5-1,9 mm; body length in females: 6,7-6,8 mm, width: 1,7-1,9 mm

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Material. Holotype, male, Russia, southern Sakhalin Is., Yuzhno-Sakhalinsk env., 24.6.1985, M. Danilevsky - MD; 26 paratypes: 22 males, 1 female with same data - MD; 1 male, southern Sakhalin Is., Kuznetsova cape, 14.6.1985, M. Danilevsky - MD; 1 male, 1 female, southern Sakhalin Is., Anna cape, 26.7.1976, V. Kuznetsov leg. - MD.

Differential diagnosis. The taxon is not close to dark *A. t. sakhalinensis* Danilevsky, 2012 distributed from central to north Sakhalin. It is very similar to rather distant Japanese *A. t. hirayamai* Fujita, 2018 distributed in Central Honshu, by differs by more elongated body with smaller and sparser punctuation.

Distribution. The taxon is distributed in south Sakhalin only.

Specimens used for comparison.

A. t. erythropus (Gebler, 1841) (= *bivittis* Motschulsky, 1860): 1 male, 1 female, Russia, Tuva Republic, Ishtii-Khem, 17.6.1972, M. Danilevsky leg. - MD; 11 males, 2 females, with same data - ML; 1 male, same locality, 20.6.1979 - MD; 1 male (with black elytra and black 1st antennal joint), Russia, Bratsk env., Angara River, 2-3.7.2006, D. Fominykh leg., - MD; 2 males, Russia, Khabarovsk region, Komsomolsky natural reserve, Gur river valley, 2.9.1975 (ex larvae from *Maackia amurensis*, 1.9.1976), M. Danilevsky - MD; 2 males, Russia, Khabarovsk region, Solnechnyi environs, Gornyi, 1992, A. Shadenkov leg. - MD.

A. t. hirayamai Fujita, 2018: 2 paratypes, 1 male, Pass Ogawara (ca. 2000 m alt.) Saku City, Nagano Pref., Honshu Is., Japan, 16.7.2014, H. Hirayama leg. - MD; 1 female, Pass Kitazawa (1980-2200 m alt.), Hase-mura, Nagano Pref., Honshu Is., Japan, 30.7.1985, H. Hirayama leg. - MD; 1 female, Yatsugatake, Shinshu, Honshu Is., Japan, 29.7.1938, Y. Chiura leg. - ML.

A. t. tenebris Danilevsky, 2012: holotype, male with the label: Russia, Primorsky Region, Kamenushka [43°37'N, 132°14'E], 2.6.1960, K. Stepanov leg. - MD; 6 paratypes: 1 male and 5 females, South Korea, Mt. Jiri, Samsinbong, 17.6.1994, T. Ueno leg. - MD; 2 males, 1 female, Russia, Vladivostok, plant garden, 14.6.2018, A. Shamaev leg. - MD; 2 males, 1 female, Russia, Primorsky Region, Lazovsky range, Lazovsky Mt., 10.7.2015, S. Ivanov leg. -

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MD; 2 females, Russia, Primorsky Region, 30 km NW Arseniev, 30.5.-4.6.2021, S. Ivanov leg. - MD.

A. t. sakhalinensis Danilevsky, 2012: holotype, male, Russia, northern Sakhalin Is., 45km SE Tymovsk, 50°39'N, 143°13'E, 19.7.2010, A. Zubov leg. - MD; 4 paratypes, females with same label - MD; 7 males 1 female, Sakhalin Is., Tymovsk environs, Diatlov stream, 50°51'18"N, 143°18'27"E, 290 m, 12.07.2010, A. Zubov leg. - MD; 1 male, Sakhalin Is., Tymovsk environs, Langari, 50°31'17"N, 142°43'40"E, 175 m, 24.06.2010, A. Zubov leg. - MD; 3 males, Sakhalin Is., Tymovsk environs, Chamginsky Pass, 50°44'40"N, 143°18'16"E, 1430 m, 1-3.06.2010, A. Zubov leg. - MD; 1 female, Sakhalin Is., Tymovsk environs, Oven river mouth, 50°40'16"N, 143°18'16"E, 340 m, 10.07. 2010, A. Zubov leg. - MD; 1 male, northern Sakhalin, Shmidta peninsula, 24.08.1973, Ivliev, Kononov leg. - MD.

Etymology. *Alosterna tabacicolor kompatsevi* **ssp. n.** is dedicated to my late colleague Alexander Kompantsev, who collected the type series many years ago. *A. t. toyohara* **ssp. n.** is named after old Japanese name of Yuzhno-Sakhalinsk - Toyohara.

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Figs 1-10. *Alosterna tabacicolor* from far east islands of Russia:

Figs 1-2. *A. t. kompantsevi* ssp. n.: 1. holotype, male; 2. paratype, female, Russia, Kunashir Is., Tretyakovo, 17.7.1977, A. Kompantsev leg.

Figs 3-10. *A. t. toyohara* ssp. n.: 3. holotype, male; 4-8. paratypes, males with same label; 9-10. paratypes, females with same label.

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